

petri dishes using a Potter's spray tower. After spraying, the larvae were transferred to untreated TN1 leaves in petri dishes.

To determine foliar toxicity, 25 ml insecticide solution was sprayed on 30-day-old plants using a bottle atomizer. Treated leaves were cut, placed in petri dishes, and infested with 10 third-instar larvae each.

Monocrotophos, diazinon, and azinphos ethyl were effective as both contact and foliar sprays (see table). Brodan, carbofuran, and methyl parathion were effective as foliar sprays.

Effect of selected insecticides on control of hairy caterpillar, 48 hours after treatment, at IRRI.

Insecticide ^a	Mortality ^b (%)	
	Contact spray	Foliar spray
Monocrotophos 16.8 EC	100.0 a	100.0 a
Diazinon 20 EC	100.0 a	100.0 a
Azinphos ethyl 40 EC	100.0 a	100.0 a
Carbofuran 20 F	32.5 b	95.0 a
Brodan (20% chlorpyrifos + 10.5% BPMC) EC	42.5 b	100.0 a
Methyl parathion 50 EC	7.5 c	82.5 a
Metalkamate 30 EC	2.5 c	0.0 c
Ethylan 45 EC	0.0 c	30.0 b
Mipcin 50 WP	0.0 c	0.0 c
Control (untreated)	0.0 c	0.0 c

^aAt 0.04% solution. ^bAv of 4 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Chemical control of azolla insects

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Insect damage is the most important limiting factor in production of azolla as a supplementary nitrogen source for rice cultivation in Thailand. Two insecticide trials were conducted on azolla at Bangkok Rice Experiment Station in 1980. The first experiment examined plant soaking in a 0.01% concentration of insecticide for 10 minutes before field inoculation and postinoculation sprays. The second compared 7 insecticides including *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bactospine) applied after field inoculation. Both experiments involved 3- × 5-m² plots in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications.

Webworm *Cryptoblabes* sp. and

caseworm *Nymphula enixalis* were the major insect pests. Azolla was damaged by insects and high temperatures during April, and by competition with blue-green algae. Monocrotophos spray gave the best insect control and highest yield (Table 1). Monocrotophos plant soak was moderately effective within 10 days

after azolla release into the field. Carbaryl was ineffective. Broadcast carbofuran provided poor insect control and azolla development. Results of the second trial confirmed that monocrotophos was the most effective insecticide among those tested for controlling defoliating insects (Table 2). Carbosulfan

Table 2. Effect of foliar insecticides sprayed on azolla insect pests at Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, Bangkok, Thailand, August 1980.

Treatment ^a	Insect infestation ^b (grade)		Fresh weight ^c (t/ha)
	10 DI	17 DI	
Monocrotophos 56% WSC	0	0	23.8 a
Carbosulfan 20% EC	++	0	21.5 ab
Chlorpyrifos 20% EC	++	0	21.0 ab
Malathion 83% EC	+++	+	17.2 abc
Fenitrothion 86% EC	++	0	15.0 bc
Bactospeine 16,000/mg	++	++	14.9 bc
Dimethoate 40% EC	++	+++	11.0 cd
Untreated control	++	+++	7.4 d

^aInsecticides were applied 1 and 10 days after field inoculation at 0.3 kg ai/ha. Bactospeine was used at 1 kg formulated product/ha. ^bIncidences of webworm and caseworm were estimated at 10 and 17 days after inoculation: 0 = no damage, + = light, ++ = moderate, +++ = severe. DI = days after inoculation. ^cMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($P = 0.05$).

Table 1. Effect of insecticide treatments on insects and azolla development at Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, Bangkok, Thailand, April 1980.^a

Treatment ^b	10 days		20 days	
	Azolla development (%)	Insect infestation	Azolla development (%)	Insect infestation
Monocrotophos spray at 1 and 10 days	70 a	0	75 a	0
Monocrotophos dip before planting	38 bc	+	0 c	+++
Monocrotophos dip and spray at 10 days	45 b	+	43 ab	++
Carbaryl spray at 1 and 10 days	23 c	++	13 bc	+++
Carbaryl dip before planting	25 c	++	0 c	+++
Carbaryl dip and spray at 10 days	23 c	++	27 bc	+++
Carbofuran broadcast at 1 and 10 days	20 c	++	0 c	+++
Untreated control	25 c	++	0 c	+++

^aAzolla development was estimated by surface area covered by azolla. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different ($p = 0.05$). Insect infestation scale: 0 = no damage, + = light, ++ = moderate, +++ = severe. ^bFoliar insecticides were sprayed at 0.5 kg ai/ha, 0.01% of insecticide solution was used for dipping, and carbofuran was applied at 1 kg ai/ha.

and chlorpyrifos were also effective. Yields of azolla treated with the three insecticides were three times greater than those of the untreated check. Bactospeine provided some insect control and caused significant yield differences com-

pared to the check.

To reduce the cost of insecticide application, it is recommended that azolla stock culture be sprayed 2-3 days before it is transferred to the propagation field. Another application is neces-

sary 7 days later. Because azolla cultivation should begin after transplanting rice, insecticide applications also affect rice insects. *h*

Efficacies of new granular and spray insecticides on rice pests

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During rainy and winter seasons of 1981-82 four granular and six spray insecticide formulations were field tested for control of seasonal pests on varieties Jaya and Tella Hamsa. Treatments were in a randomized block design and three replications.

Granular formulations of endosulfan, thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate, bendio-

carb, and phorate were applied at 1.0 and 0.5 kg ai/ha and compared with maximum protection and an untreated control. Spray formulations of fenvalerate, isofenphos, bendiocarb, carbosulfan, thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate, and phosalone were applied at 0.5 and 0.35 kg ai/ha and compared with an untreated check.

Insecticides were applied at 30, 50, and 90 days after transplanting (DT) after pretreatment insect counts were recorded. Counts were made by dividing the plot into four quadrats and randomly selecting six hills from each quadrat.

Tillers and deadhearts (DH) were counted to determine percent DH; panicle bearing tillers and whiteheads (WH) were counted to determine percent WH; and leaves and leaf folder-damaged leaves (LFDL) were counted for percent LFDL. Grain yields were calculated after eliminating two border rows from all sides.

During both seasons, yellow stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* was the predominant pest. Leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* caused 20% leaf damage on the rainy season crop.

Thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate was

Efficacies of granular and spray insecticide formulations, Warangal, India, 1981-82.^a

Insecticide	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Rainy season				Winter season			
		Yellow stem borer deadhearts (%)		Leaf folder damaged leaves (%)		Yellow stem borer deadhearts (%)			Yield (t/ha)
		50 DT	90 DT	60 DT		30 DT	50 DT	90 DT	
<i>Granular formulation</i>									
Endosulfan	1.0	13.4 ab	8.1 a	16.7 c	2.7 d	12.7 bc	6.5 b	9.9 ab	4.2 b
-do-	0.5	13.7 a	9.6 a	16.8 bc	3.3 c	17.8 b	9.5 a	8.1 bcd	3.4 c
Evisect	1.0	3.0 e	0.8 d	3.0 f	4.4 a	8.0 cd	0.3 d	3.5 c	5.3 a
-do-	0.5	3.7 e	1.3 d	4.1 f	4.2ab	10.4 cd	0.7 d	4.4 e	5.0 a
Bendiocarb	1.0	9.0 c	8.5 a	11.9 d	3.3 c	17.8 b	9.7 a	11.0 a	2.0 cd
-do-	0.5	11.4 b	7.9 a	16.1 c	2.6 d	23.7 a	7.6 ab	6.9 d	2.3 e
Phorate	1.0	9.0 c	5.7 b	6.8 e	3.0 cd	6.0 d	0.4 d	7.3 cd	5.2 a
Maximum protection treatment ^a	1.0	6.2 d	3.8 c	5.9 e	3.8 b	6.3 d	2.8 c	2.6 f	5.1 a
Untreated control A	-	14.1 a	8.7 a	20.1 a	2.1 e	27.2 a	7.7 ab	9.3 abc	2.2 e
Untreated control B	-	14.1 a	9.6 a	19.2 ab	1.7 e	27.0a	8.6 ab	9.5 abc	2.7 de
<i>Spray formulation</i>									
Fenvalerate	0.3	15.4 ab	7.9 bc	1.9 fg	2.8 b	7.9 cde	8.3 de	8.7 bcde	4.3 bc
-do-	0.15	17.8 a	12.7 a	2.5 ef	1.8 ef	12.6 b	17.6 abc	8.0 cde	3.9 d
Isofenphos	0.5	4.1 e	3.6 ef	6.6 c	3.9 a	-	-	-	-
-do-	0.35	9.8 c	5.1 c	8.5 b	2.9 b	-	-	-	-
Bendiocarb	0.5	14.2 b	6.2 cd	2.2 efg	1.8 ef	12.6 bc	14.6 bc	11.0abc	4.1 cd
-do-	0.35	13.8 c	6.4 cd	2.0 g	2.2 cde	13.9 b	14.4 bc	12.6 a	3.9 d
Carbosulfan	0.5	6.5 d	3.1 fg	2.9 e	2.5 bcd	3.7 f	2.7 f	7.4 e	5.0a
-do-	0.35	9.2 c	3.4 fg	0.9 f	3.0 b	8.0 ef	8.9 e	12.1 ab	4.5 b
Evisect	0.5	6.6 d	2.2 g	1.7 g	3.8 a	9.8 bcde	4.3 f	3.7 f	5.1 a
-do-	0.35	6.4 d	2.5 fg	2.8 ef	2.7 bc	8.0 de	6.0 ef	7.8 de	4.5 b
Phosalone	0.5	14.5 b	8.6 b	4.5 d	1.7 ef	12.1 bcd	12.2 cd	10.7 abcd	4.0 cd
Maximum protection treatment ^b		6.5 d	0.8 h	1.9 fg	3.0 b	6.7 ef	9.8 ef	1.7 g	5.1 a
Untreated control		17.6 a	12.6 a	9.9 a	1.5 f	21.6a	21.2a	10.7 abcd	2.9 c

^aIn a row, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bInvolves seedling root dip with 0.02% chlorpyrifos; carbosulfan application at 1 kg ai/ha, at 20, 40, and 60 days after transplanting (DT); and quinalphos spray at 0.3 kg ai/ha, at 75 DT.